

Hydrogen storage in lithium adsorbed and polyolithiated (OLi₂) heteroatom (B, N) modified (2,2) γ -graphyne nanotube and its CO sensing potential: A computational study[†]

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We have investigated the hydrogen storage potential of Li atom adsorbed and OLi₂ functionalized (2,2) γ -graphyne nanotube (GNT), using density functional theory based calculations. We have found that Li atom prefers to stay on the trigonal pole (TP) of γ -GNT whereas OLi₂ is strongly adsorbed on B atom of B, N-doped hexagonal ring site connected with acetylenic linkage, which is desirable for H₂ storage. In presence of a small polar molecule OLi₂ exploits the hydrogen storage ability more than that in the bare γ -GNT as well as the Li-adsorbed γ -GNT. The thermodynamical stability of hydrogen loaded γ -GNT is studied using binding energies, and change in reaction enthalpies.

The maximum retrievable H₂ uptake predicted that eight H₂ molecules can be physically adsorbed in non-dissociated form per OLi₂. The stability and reactivity of these hydrogen-adhered species are analyzed through the energy gap between the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO).

Exohedral CO sorption behaviour on Li-doped γ -GNT is also analyzed here.

Keywords: Hydrogen storage, B-N doped γ -Graphyne nanotube, polyolithiation, thermochemical stability, CO adsorption.

Introduction

Owing to an increase in the world population, demands for higher standards of living, growth in industries, number of automobiles and that of energy have been increasing significantly. An underlying problem of the energy industry is that the rate of formation of fossil fuels is much slower than the rate of their consumption. Further, the majority of the fossil fuels cause pollution by generating green house gases during burning and this affect our health as well as the environment. These serious disadvantages signify the need to search for alternative energy resources which are abundant, sustainable, renewable and environment-friendly. Hydrogen, which is known to be the most abundant gas in this universe, is a clean energy source as only water vapour is produced on its burning. It can be produced by electrolysis or photolysis of water, and its oxidation produces no greenhouse gas.

Various literature surveys have shown that hydrogen pos-

sesses about three times higher gravimetric energy density than the current energy resources such as methane and gasoline. However, safe and efficient storage of hydrogen, which links its production and final use, under ambient conditions is a challenging task. Being a flammable, low-density gas, its storage in liquid form (in cryogenic tanks or high pressure tanks) is much more difficult and unsafe than that for liquid hydrocarbons. Pd metal has been used as an alternative hydrogen storage material, but Pd being a heavy metal, this storage form is not suitable for widespread commercial applications. It also does not meet the requirements of the storage target of the US Department of Energy^{1,2}.

In order that the desorption process undergoes smoothly under room temperature, the interaction energy with the molecular adsorbate must be in between those of physisorption and chemisorption³. Earlier report by Züttel *et al.*⁴ suggests that H₂ adsorption takes place via a surface adsorption mechanism on single wall carbon nanotubes.

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Particularly, acid-treated hybrid composite materials of multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) and MOF-5 have been synthesized by Yang *et al.*⁵, for hydrogen adsorption purpose and they observed 50% increment in hydrogen storage capacity of this material at 77 K and 1 bar. Wang *et al.*⁶ studied the hydrogen adsorption capacity due to functionalization of the microporous metal organic framework (MMOF) at a low pressure. They stated that adsorption of gas molecules is remarkably governed by adsorbate-adsorbent interaction. Recently, Guo *et al.*⁷ discussed hydrogen storage capacity of a hierarchical structure of graphene material. The hydrogen uptake capacity is considerably higher (over 4.0 weight percent) than some other kinds of carbon based materials along with the previously reported graphene materials as well.

On the other hand, carbon monoxide is a highly toxic gas for hemoglobin animals. The maximum tolerance limit of CO is ~50 ppm in air for a time weighted average limit (TWA). Carbon monoxide poisoning mainly occurs due to the combination of CO with hemoglobin (Hb) producing carboxyhemoglobin (HbCO) which hinders Hb's ability to deliver oxygen to the body since affinity of Hb towards CO is much more (approximately 200 times) than that towards O₂⁸. Thus, removal of CO from the environment is very important, which can be done by using CO adsorbent materials. Furthermore, CO adsorption is essential in certain heterogeneous catalytic reactions.

Santucci *et al.*⁹ have investigated a theoretical as well as experimental study of NO₂ and CO gas sensing capability of CNT based materials. There is also a report on CO adsorption process on the surface of BN, AlN, BP and AlP nanotubes using DFT¹⁰⁻¹² calculations¹³. Recently, a simulation study for the detection of CO and H₂O using carbon nanotubes as new molecular sensors have been made by Peng and Cho¹⁴ via doping impurity atoms. Some important relevant studies are also made to get more insights into the adsorption process^{15,16}.

In the modern era, the mankind has encountered with two major problems namely energy crisis and environmental pollution. Hence, we have tried to investigate adsorption of H₂ and CO respectively on recently reported B, N modified γ -GNT¹⁷ where only one Li atom is adsorbed on TP ring of the nanotube. To improve hydrogen storage capacity we have functionalized B, N modified GNT with OLi₂ as a group of

atoms. It is noted that gas storage media having large surface area should preferably be composed of light elements and carbon based nanostructures, which are considered to be the most promising physisorption substrates for hydrogen storage. However, due to the inertness in the pure form of carbon based nanostructures, these are not suitable for use in most of the technological purposes unless functionalized with heteroatoms. The existence of molecules possessing a high density of lithium atoms (Li), known as polyolithiated molecules, which include CLi_n and OLi_m (n = 3–5 and m = 1–4), has been verified in many experimental as well as theoretical studies^{18–21}. In the present investigation, we have separately elucidated the hydrogen storage potential of a single adsorbed Li atom (above the triangle pole, TP, the most stable position) and OLi₂ bound γ -graphyne nanotube in which B and N heteroatoms are doped at the hexagonal rings joined together by acetylenic linkages which surround to form a large triangle pole. Especially, due to the polar nature of O-Li bond of OLi₂ and electron deficiency in B atom, a significant amount of positive charge is left on Li atoms, which induces polarization and is able to trap hydrogen (H₂) molecules, thus finding an important application as a hydrogen storage material with good storing capabilities²².

For the sake of brevity, now onwards B-N doped γ -graphyne nanotube will be denoted as γ -GNT.

Computational details

The geometry optimization and subsequent frequency analysis of all the systems have been carried out using ω B97X-D functional, a long range corrected significantly better functional for interpretation of non-bonded interactions, developed by Chai and Head-Gordon²³. This functional uses a version of Grimme's D2 dispersion model²⁴. Due to the large size of our studied system 6-31G (d,p) basis set is used. Existence of all the real values of frequencies (NIMAG = 0) ensure that the studied systems under investigation correspond to minima on their concerned potential energy surfaces (PES). To calculate average binding energies (E_b), thermochemical parameters such as change in enthalpies (ΔH) per H₂ molecule, the following expression has been used.

$$E_b(n) = 1/n[E_{\text{nH}_2 \cdots \text{systems}} - \{(E_{\text{systems}} + nE_{\text{H}_2})\}]$$

All these computations are done using Gaussian 09 program package²⁵. The natural population analysis (NPA)²⁶ scheme is adopted to compute atomic charges (QNPA).

Results and discussion

(A) Structure, stability and reaction energies:

We have taken a unit of (2,2) γ -graphyne nanotube which is alternatively doped with B and N at the hexagonal rings which are connected by acetylenic linkages (-C \equiv C-), surrounding pores larger than densely packed honeycomb lattice in graphene²⁷. Out of several varieties of graphyne, we have considered this type of theoretically reported¹⁷ γ -GNT modified with B, N hetero atoms having 21.85 wt.% B, 28.29 wt.% N and 33.33% acetylenic linkage. In the present study we have separately investigated the thermochemical stability with respect to binding of our studied species adsorbed with Li atom along with its H₂ and CO adsorbing capacity, and that functionalized with polyolithiated species like OLi₂ along with its H₂ trapping ability.

Inspired by the prior reports that Li shows superior performance for H₂ storage, we have predicted the most acceptable OLi₂ ad-atoms functionalized γ -GNT where a small polar molecule OLi₂ is attached on the electron deficient B atom so that B and O atoms together leave positive charges on the Li atom, making it suitable for H₂ trapping. The optimized structures of γ -GNT, Li adsorbed γ -GNT (i.e. BLi) and OLi₂ decorated γ -GNT (i.e. BOLI₂) are given in Fig. 1.

In the free molecular state, O-Li bond length and \angle LiOLi bond angle were determined as 1.63 Å and 180° respectively. After binding with B atom of hexagonal BN (h-BN) site,

the minimum energy structures possess an O-Li distance of 1.91 Å and \angle LiOLi of 102° (see Fig. 1). The relaxed structure of the studied molecule also indicates the tilting of Li atoms towards the center of triangle pole (TP) formed by acetylenic linkage, which implies that Li atoms attain the most favourable positions in those TP holes. The binding energy (E_b) of Li unit and OLi₂ unit on γ -GNT has been calculated as:

$$E_{b(\text{OLi}_2)} = E(\text{BOLI}_2) - \{E(\text{B}) + E(\text{OLi}_2)\}$$

$$E_{b(\text{Li})} = E(\text{BLi}) - \{E(\text{B}) + E(\text{Li})\}$$

where $E(\text{BOLI}_2)$, $E(\text{B})$, $E(\text{OLi}_2)$, $E(\text{BLi})$ and $E(\text{Li})$ are the total energies of BOLI₂ (C₄₈H₁₆N₂₄B₂₄OLi₂), B (C₄₈H₁₆N₂₄B₂₄), OLi₂, BLi (C₄₈H₁₆N₂₄B₂₄Li) and Li respectively. The binding energy for BOLI₂ species is calculated to be -106.7 kcal/mol, whereas that of BLi species is -79.6 kcal/mol.

The thermochemical stability of BOLI₂ with respect to binding of OLi₂ on γ -GNT can be understood from the corresponding change in enthalpy (ΔH) and free energy (ΔG) values computed at 298 K which are -106.7 kcal/mol and -94.4 kcal/mol respectively. Similarly, that for BLi are -79.6 kcal/mol and -72.2 kcal/mol respectively. The negative values of ΔH and ΔG for the formation process imply that the formation of BOLI₂ and BLi is exothermic as well as exergonic in nature. The decoration of OLi₂ unit on γ -GNT brings quite a substantial change in HOMO-LUMO energy gap ($\Delta E_{\text{H-L}}$). Upon binding the energy of HOMO of γ -GNT gets stabilized and energy of LUMO gets destabilized resulting in

Fig. 1. Geometries of γ -GNT, BLi and BOLI₂ optimized at the ω B97X-D/6-31G(d,p) level of theory.

an increase in ΔE_{H-L} by 0.41 eV. As ΔE_{H-L} is related to the chemical hardness the system gets stabilized as dictated by the maximum hardness principle²⁸.

(B) Hydrogen storage capacity:

From first-principle theoretical calculations it is found that Li atom can bind strongly to the $sp^2 + sp^1$ hybridized carbon network of graphyne²⁹ and each Li can capture up to maximum three H_2 molecules^{29,22}. To compare the previous results with that from our present investigation we have carried out lithiation on B, N doped γ -GNT followed by the hydrogen loading process on the BLi. Our result also suggests that single lithium can uptake a maximum of three H_2 molecules and the fourth one is found to move far away from the Li site (see Fig. 2).

Again, previous studies on polyolithiated graphane systems have shown that each Li atom can adsorb at the most three H_2 molecules i.e. six H_2 molecules per unit of OLi_2 ²². We have started by adsorbing one H_2 molecule to the optimized $BOLi_2$ structure. Similarly we have proceeded with two, three, and so on up to eight H_2 molecules where each Li atom can trap three H_2 simultaneously with two H_2 by the O atom. The H_2 adsorbed minimum energy structures on po-

tential energy surface (PES) are shown in Fig. 3. The binding energy (E_b) per H_2 molecule has been calculated as:

$$E_b = 1/n [E(nH_2 \cdots BOLi_2) - \{E(BOLi_2) + E(nH_2)\}]$$

The average binding energy ranges between -2.62 kcal/mol and -3.28 kcal/mol.

To know further about the thermodynamics of H_2 trapping process, we have defined the sequential binding energy of the n -th H_2 molecule using the formula:

$$E_b(n) = E\{BOLi_2 + (n-1)H_2\} + E(H_2) - E\{BOLi_2 + nH_2\}$$

where $E\{BOLi_2 + nH_2\}$, $E\{BOLi_2 + (n-1)H_2\}$ are the total energies with n and $(n-1)$ H_2 molecules adsorbed, respectively and $E(H_2)$ is the total energy of a single H_2 molecule. The negative value of binding energy corresponds to stable configuration and the negative value of enthalpy change highlights that the adsorption process is exothermic in nature.

Due to much larger electronegativity of O atom than those of B and Li, each Li atom which is directly bonded to the O atom in OLi_2 species, acquires a positive charge while the O acquires a negative charge. Li atom bearing this high amount of charge on it facilitates the electrostatic interaction with H_2 molecules to get adsorbed on Li atoms. Again negative charge

Fig. 2. Geometries of $H_2 \cdots BLi$ optimized at the $\omega B97X-D/6-31G(d,p)$ level of theory.

on O atom polarizes H₂ molecules and thus can adsorb there (see Fig. 3). In this study, we have found that the O atom of OLi₂ adsorbs at the most two H₂ molecules.

The binding energies and enthalpies of all the nH₂...BOLi₂ systems are given in Table 1. As we can see, the binding energy gradually increases with the successive loading of H₂ molecules, apart from the 3rd one (see Fig. 4). The adsorption enthalpy values of all the H₂ binding processes are negative which indicates that the adsorption processes are

exothermic in nature and these processes may be thermodynamically spontaneous requiring cryogenic temperature when the favorable ΔH term overcomes the unfavorable $T\Delta S$ term giving negative values for ΔG term.

From the natural population analysis (NPA) it has been observed that the positive charge on Li center gradually decreases with the number of bound H₂ showing some degree of electron transfer from H₂ molecule to Li center of OLi₂ group (see Table 2).

Fig. 3. Structures of nH₂...BOLi₂ optimized at the ω B97X-D/6-31G (d, p) level where n = 1–8.

Table 1. Adsorption enthalpy (ΔH , kcal/mol) and binding energy (E_b , kcal/mol) of nH₂...BOLi₂ (where BOLi₂ is C₄₈H₁₆N₂₄B₂₄OLi₂, and n = 1-8)

Process	ΔG per H ₂	ΔH per H ₂	E_b per H ₂
H ₂ + BOLi ₂ → H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	4.687	-1.615	-3.279
H ₂ + H ₂ ...BOLi ₂ → 2H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	4.701	-1.544	-3.257
H ₂ + 2H ₂ ...BOLi ₂ → 3H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	4.687	-1.691	-3.312
H ₂ + 3H ₂ ...BOLi ₂ → 4H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	5.028	-1.662	-3.265
H ₂ + 4H ₂ ...BOLi ₂ → 5H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	5.215	-1.470	-3.087
H ₂ + 5H ₂ ...BOLi ₂ → 6H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	5.435	-1.398	-3.006
H ₂ + 6H ₂ ...BOLi ₂ → 7H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	5.473	-1.235	-2.814
H ₂ + 7H ₂ ...BOLi ₂ → 8H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	5.573	-1.120	-2.620

(C) CO adsorption:

CO molecules can be adsorbed in two different ways. First, when CO molecules bind with the carbon end it is found to interact with the Li atom adsorbed at the top of TP ring, and secondly, the presence of relatively more electron rich O atoms in CO molecules stimulates the possibility of interaction with the adsorbed Li atom. Between these two different ways of interaction in both C-bound and O-bound conformations are minima on the potential energy surface, O-side binding is less favourable than the C-side binding by

Fig. 4. Variation of binding energy per H₂ molecule with the number of hydrogen molecules adsorbed calculated at ω B97X-D/6-31G (d, p) level of theory.

2.61 kcal/mol. Successive adsorption of CO molecules up to a maximum of three in an exohedral fashion are shown in

Table 2. NBO charges on Li and O atoms of all the nH₂...BOLi₂ systems

System	q _{Li}	q _O
OLi ₂	0.739	-1.479
γ -GNT		
BOLi ₂	0.780	-1.113
H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	0.769-0.707	-1.110
2H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	0.711-0.682	-1.101
3H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	0.678-0.633	-1.100
4H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	0.635-0.622	-1.096
5H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	0.635-0.607	-1.105
6H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	0.631-0.603	-1.104
7H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	0.609-0.602	-1.105
8H ₂ ...BOLi ₂	0.626-0.602	-1.120
BLi	0.828	
H ₂ ...BLi	0.735	
2H ₂ ...BLi	0.672	
3H ₂ ...BLi	0.598	
OC...BLi	0.607	
2OC...BLi	0.436	
3OC...BLi	0.248	

Fig. 5. Geometries of OC...BLi optimized at the ω B97X-D/6-31G(d,p) level of theory.

Figs. 5 and 6 and the corresponding adsorption energies of -29.33 kcal/mol, -18.91 kcal/mol and -15.35 kcal/mol respectively are given in Table 3. The CO adsorption process is exothermic in nature ($\Delta H = -27.32$ kcal/mol, -17.40 kcal/mol and -14.04 kcal/mol). The following results suggest that CO molecules interact significantly with the BLi. The C–O distance in free state of CO is 1.135 Å whereas it is 1.128 – 1.131 Å for C-side binding case and 1.140 – 1.144 Å for O-side binding case, which suggest that the C–O distance undergoes a very little decrease in the C-bound case and a slight increase in the O-bound case upon adsorption (see

Table 4). The harmonic frequency calculations infer an insignificant blue-shift and red-shift in stretching frequency in those two cases respectively. However, it is found that exohedral CO adsorption also has no effect on the nanotube structure. What happens to this structure in solution phase that remains to be assessed^{30,31}.

Table 4. Change in bond length and frequency

Systems	Δr_{L-L} (Å)	ν_{C-O} (cm ⁻¹)	$\Delta \nu$ (cm ⁻¹)
CO		2245	
nOC...BLi	-0.004 to -0.007	2282–2306	37 to 61
nCO...BLi	0.005 to 0.009	2200–2217	-28 to -45

Fig. 6. Geometries of CO...BLi optimized at the ω B97X-D/6-31G(d,p) level of theory.

Table 3. Adsorption enthalpy (ΔH , kcal/mol) and binding energy (E_b , kcal/mol) of nOC...BLi/nCO...BLi (where BLi is C₄₈H₁₆N₂₄B₂₄Li and n = 1–38)

Process	ΔG per CO	ΔH per CO	E_b per CO
CO + BOLI ₂ → OC...BOLI ₂	-20.04	-27.32	-29.33
CO + OC...BOLI ₂ → 2OC...BOLI ₂	-9.41	-17.40	-18.91
CO + 2OC...BOLI ₂ → 3OC...BOLI ₂	-5.98	-14.04	-15.35
Process	ΔG per CO	ΔH per CO	E_b per CO
CO + BOLI ₂ → CO...BOLI ₂	-18.37	-24.94	-26.72
CO + CO...BOLI ₂ → 2CO...BOLI ₂	-7.82	-15.18	-16.50
CO + 2CO...BOLI ₂ → 3CO...BOLI ₂	-4.39	-13.01	-13.22

Conclusion

Using DFT calculations, it has been shown that the systematic functionalization by a small polar molecule OLi_2 on B atom of h-BN site of γ -GNT can tune the H_2 storage capacity. The calculated binding energy infers that the structure of BOLi_2 is thermodynamically stable with respect to its dissociation into OLi_2 and γ -GNT. The polar natures of B-O and Li-O bonds have been characterized on the basis of NBO charge analysis. It has been found that the positively charged Li atom on one OLi_2 molecule can adsorb up to three H_2 molecules and the negatively charged O atom can absorb up to two H_2 molecules, resulting in adsorption of eight H_2 molecules per OLi_2 group which is a significant improvement in the hydrogen storage capacity of functionalized γ -GNT over only bare moiety as well as the Li-adsorbed γ -GNT. The average binding energies of H_2 molecules have been found to be within the range useful for practical applications.

In the case of CO trapping, the Li-adsorbed γ -GNT leads to thermodynamically stable CO bound compound through both the carbon and oxygen centers, viz. $\text{OC}\cdots\text{BLi}$ and $\text{CO}\cdots\text{BLi}$. All the Li centers get positively charged and the amount of charge transfer is significant and the parent moiety holds a maximum of up to three CO molecules. Furthermore, a careful scrutiny of the computed harmonic vibrational frequencies on gas trapping capacity of this Li-adsorbed and OLi_2 functionalized γ -GNT revealed that H-H IR stretching frequencies ($\nu_{\text{H-H}}$) remains almost unaltered in case of the H_2 adsorption whereas a little change (blue shift for C-bound case or red shift for O-bound case) can be found in case of the CO adsorption with almost unchanged bond lengths. It is worth mentioning that these theoretical predictions may encourage experimentalists to search for effective hydrogen storage materials in future.

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